

STUDY OF GENDER STEREOTYPES IN MILITARY FAMILIES IN PSYCHOLOGICAL RESEARCH

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Annotation: the article discusses the use of the concept of gender, the importance of stereotypes, the interpretation of theoretical views, their introduction into psychology, and the essence of social gender culture. The article also reveals that different researchers understand the term “gender stereotypes” differently: this is a schematized set of ideas about the personal characteristics of men and women; these are schematic, generalized images of masculinity and femininity; these are socially constructed categories of “masculinity” and “femininity”, which describe different behaviors, social roles of men and women depending on gender.

Keywords: man, woman, gender, brain, consciousness, concept, value, culture, genetic, term, connection, problem, sphere, relative.

In the political sphere, at the stage under consideration, there is a change in the forms and pace of women's integration into power, which is expressed in the fact that over the past six years, Russian women have taken firm positions in the middle echelons of Russian state power, as well as began to conquer its higher echelons. Men, being at the highest echelons of power, do not feel the need to change this situation in the current situation, which may begin to change their gender ideas. Therefore, such a division of the position of men and women in the political sphere does not practically change men's views on the recognition of partnership between women and men in politics. At the same time, innovative gender practices of women in this sphere have a certain impact on the weakening of traditional gender views in Russian society. New gender concepts include the recognition of the variability of women's positions in the political sphere, which is expressed in the fact that a woman can have power, be subject to power, and strive for power. In this regard, the traditional views of military personnel, which define the subordinate role of women

in the army, are changing, allowing for the approximation of the role positions of male and female military personnel in the army. In the economic sphere, there is also a tendency to reduce the degree of rigidity in the hierarchy of relations between men and women, which leads to the liberalization of their gender interaction. This trend is determined, first of all, by the ongoing positive dynamics of the economic activity of female representatives, which is manifested in the emergence of a new social cohort of "successful women", as well as the strengthening of the position of Russian women. The dynamics of gender relations in the economic sphere is characterized by an expansion of the repertoire of women's social roles in the social sphere, as well as the depolarization of the socio-psychological characteristics of men and women. The market model of the economy allows women to freely develop their initiative, independence and independence in choosing forms of work, and thereby determines the need for women to change their behavior and consciousness. In this regard, they are developing new social relations that determine the equalization of opportunities for men and women in the social sphere. Men, interacting with women who show business activity, also change their gender concepts. In their minds, femininity is no longer interpreted as a purely "passive-reproductive principle" manifested in expressive personal characteristics. These trends determine the change in the gender concepts of military personnel, which is expressed in the recognition that in the army, women can realize themselves in certain types of military professional activity if they have the personal characteristics of the activity (initiative, mobility, communication skills, ability to work in a team, organization, responsibility, etc.). It should be noted that the professional sphere in 2002-2008. characterized by a gradual liberalization of gender relations, which is determined by a decrease in the level of occupational segregation by sex. This trend is determined, firstly, by the expansion of women's access to certain "male" fields of activity and the active entry of men into "female" professions; secondly, by increasing the level of women's qualifications in both "female" and "male" professional fields. Women are increasingly choosing professional fields that are "unfavorable" from the point of view of their dual employment (at work and at home). The integration of women

into non-traditional professions determines the replacement of "old" beliefs with "new" ones in society, which significantly hinder their adaptation to the "male" professional environment. Professionalism as a social characteristic is based on the fact that there is no gender difference in any profession, including those defined as "male". In this regard, according to the author of the dissertation, it is possible to change the gender concepts of military personnel, which are expressed in a combination of patriarchal and liberal views on the role and place of women in "male" professions and, in particular, in the field of military-professional activity. The dynamics of the individualization of men and women in Russian society, in the face of demographic risks and their growing desire for self-realization, determines the flexibility of their role positions in the family sphere. The family, as a rule, does not limit the possibilities and aspirations of women for self-realization, thereby expanding its boundaries within the community, sometimes at the expense of its own resources. It should be noted that the dynamics of the gender structure of the Russian army was to some extent influenced by the increase in the quantitative and qualitative composition of female servicemen in the total and gender-differentiated population of military personnel. It was found that from 2002 to 2008 the share of female servicemen increased by almost 3.5% and amounted to almost 10% of the total number of military personnel in the Russian army. The share of female servicemen in the officer ranks also increased. This is explained by the expansion of the list of military positions filled by female servicemen since 2004, as well as an increase in the share of qualified female servicemen with higher military education. In this regard, the author concludes that the increase in the numerical representation of female servicemen and the differentiated gender composition of this socio-professional group contribute to their less consideration as a "special" category of military personnel. Thus, the marginal position of women in society as military specialists is determined, which allows them to realize themselves and advance in the military-professional environment, but not yet on equal terms with men. According to scientists, the increase in the quality level of female military personnel in the period from 2002 to 2008 is determined by a significant increase in the number

of women demonstrating innovative gender practices during this period. It should be noted that the predominance of female military personnel in this category is associated with the dynamics of their level of military professional orientation (MPO), as well as the strengthening of androgynous and masculine characteristics necessary for successful professionalization in the military environment. The dynamics of the level of military professional orientation of female military personnel at the studied stage is determined by a decrease in the share of women with a low and average level of military professional orientation, as well as an increase in the share of women with a high level of military professional orientation. From the content of the dissertation research it follows that female military personnel with higher professional education are distinguished by an active professional position, expressed in clearly defined professional goals. For the category of female military personnel with medium and low levels of higher education, it is customary to consider the military profession as a mandatory necessity. At the same time, they are distinguished by a weakly expressed direction of professional aspirations and the absence of clearly defined professional goals. According to the data of the conducted sociological research, from 2002 to 2008, the share of female military personnel with medium and low levels of VPO decreased from 65% to 40%, while those with high levels of VPO increased by 25% and amounted to 60%. This trend is determined, first of all, by the dynamics of women's motivational choice of a military profession, which is determined by the predominance of professionally oriented motives; secondly, by increasing the number of female military personnel with higher military education, the foundation for their military-professional direction is laid; thirdly, by increasing the level of socio-legal support for female military personnel, this creates increasingly favorable conditions for their military and professional self-expression at each stage of military service.

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